

Building a Low-cost UAV-based LiDAR Sensor for Landscape Archaeology

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Abstract

LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) point cloud data is becoming increasingly important in archaeological field work. Used to develop digital elevation (DEM), digital terrain (DTM), and digital surface models (DSM), particularly in areas of dense vegetation, it has applications in archaeological prospection, site survey, and cultural heritage management and monitoring to name just a few (Opitz, 2016, p. 35). While some areas, such as the United States of America, have publicly available LiDAR data for large areas of the country, LiDAR data may not be available, or difficult to access, for other countries. Regional LiDAR surveys can be expensive undertakings, and even localized drone-based systems typically cost tens to hundreds of thousands of dollars. For this reason alone, LiDAR technology is out of the budgetary ranges of many archaeological projects. This paper addresses this problem by building a low-cost LiDAR sensor for use on unoccupied aerial vehicles (UAV).

The LiDAR sensor for this project is based upon the Open Mobile Mapping System, OpenMMS v1.3, an open-source project developed by Ryan G. Brazeal as part of his doctoral degree research in Geomatics at the University of Florida to build a mapping system for use on remotely piloted aircraft systems/unoccupied aircraft systems (RPAS/UAS) (*Welcome – The OpenMMS Project 2021*). The OpenMMS project provides complete details to build a sensor including software for data collection and initial processing, hardware specifications, and even printed circuit board design files, however, the system uses an expensive Applanix APX-18 GNSS-INS sensor. According to a forum post by Brazeal the total cost for the Applanix APX-18 INS (Inertial Navigation System) sensor, two Trimble AV14 GNSS antennae, and the commercial POSPac UAV software is \$21,602 USD (*Welcome – The OpenMMS Project 2021*).

This paper demonstrates the feasibility of building a lower cost solution based on the OpenMMS project and the Livox Mid-40 LiDAR sensor but replacing the expensive Applanix INS sensor with a custom solution using off-the-shelf GPS/GNSS (Global Positioning System/Global Navigation Satellite System) modules and integrating a less expensive inertial measurement unit (IMU) to form an inertial navigation system (INS). Results of testing the system at the first century A.D. Roman site of Antiochia ad Cragum in south-central Turkey in 2022 are also presented.

Keywords: LiDAR, UAV, Drone, Archaeology, Landscape archaeology, GNSS, GPS

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Introduction

Airborne laser scanning, or LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), has been used for archaeological prospection, survey, and cultural heritage management for two decades and is increasing (Opitz, 2016, p. 35; Chapman, 2006, p. 58; Grammer et al., 2017, p. 312). LiDAR is an active remote sensing technique in which timed pulses of laser light are directed at a surface. By calculating the time differential between transmission of the pulse and its return, the distance to the surface can be calculated (Campbell et al., 2002, p. 237; Lillesand et al., 2004, p. 725). LiDAR cameras are typically mounted on aircraft, and in order to be used for remote sensing a digital LiDAR camera requires accurate orientation, positioning, and heading information for the aircraft. Orientation information is provided by an inertial measurement unit (IMU) and position and heading information is provided by GPS. Using a terrestrial base station and differential postprocessing corrections each point can be precisely georeferenced (Figure 1) (Campbell et al., 2002, p. 237; Lillesand et al., 2004, pp. 725–8).

LiDAR's usefulness lies in its ability to record multiple returns. Primary returns are reflected from the first objects the laser pulse detects, which may be the top of the vegetation canopy, roofs of buildings, or other unobstructed objects (Campbell et al., 2002, p. 237). A portion of the pulse may also pass through gaps in the vegetation and be reflected by lower objects, including the ground surface, generating secondary returns (Campbell et al., 2002, pp. 238–9). By applying filtering techniques digital elevation models (DEM) and digital terrain models (DTM) can be generated. If the LiDAR sensor supports capture of reflectance values the data can be filtered by intensity (Lillesand et al., 2004, pp. 729–30). Another form of LiDAR is the full waveform sensor, which allows changing the beam width and is designed to store the entire waveform (White, 2013, p. 179).

Smaller and lighter LiDAR cameras are making UAV-based systems more widely available. Adams et al. recently utilized a Zenmuse L1 LiDAR sensor carried by a Matrice 300 RTK UAV, both from the drone manufacturer DJI, as part of a multi-spectral survey of the Roman Legionary Base of Legio VI Ferrata near Tel Megiddo in Israel to determine the extent of the camp itself (Adams, Matthew J. and Ernenwein, Eileen and Laugomer, Ben and Schicht, Ido and Tepper, Yatom, n.d.). Adams further stated the UAV was able to survey an area of 2 sq km in one flight at an altitude of 35m, demonstrating the utility of UAV-based LiDAR sensors in archaeological survey (Adams, Matthew J. and Ernenwein, Eileen and Laugomer, Ben and Schicht, Ido and Tepper, Yatom, n.d.). DJI's website lists the cost of the Zenmuse L1 sensor alone at \$14,300, while the base cost of the Matrice 300 RTK is listed at \$13,700 ([Buy Zenmuse L1 - DJI Store 2021](#)). The purpose of this study is to determine if it is feasible to build a lower cost LiDAR system for use on a UAV.

Material and methods

The OpenMMS Project

The LiDAR sensor for this project is based upon the Open Mobile Mapping System, OpenMMS v1.3, an open source project developed by Ryan G. Brazeal as part of his doctoral degree research in Geomatics at the University of Florida to build a mapping system for use on remotely piloted aircraft systems/unoccupied aircraft systems (RPAS/UAS) ([Project History – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation 2021](#)). The OpenMMS project provides complete

44 details to build a sensor based on the project including software for data collection and initial
45 processing, hardware specifications, and even printed circuit board design files ([Welcome – The
46 OpenMMS Project 2021](#)). Initially the project used an Applanix APX-15 v2 GNSS-INS (Global
47 Navigation Satellite System/Inertial Navigation System) sensor with a Velodyne VLP-16 LiDAR
48 sensor ([Project History – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation 2021](#)). In version 1.2
49 the Applanix INS sensor was upgraded to the Applanix APX-18 GNSS-INS sensor but still used
50 the Velodyne LiDAR sensor ([Project History – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation
51 2021](#)). In version 1.3 with the release of the Livox Mid-40 LiDAR sensor the project released
52 two versions, one with the Velodyne LiDAR sensor and another using the Livox Mid-40 LiDAR
53 sensor, however, both systems still used the very expensive Applanix APX-18 INS sensor ([Open-
54 MMS Hardware – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation 2021](#); [Applanix Alternative
55 2021](#)). According to a forum post by Brazeal the total cost for the Applanix APX-18 INS sen-
56 sor, two Trimble AV14 GNSS antennae, and the commercial POSPac UAV software is \$21,602
57 which represents 80% of the total cost of using the Velodyne LiDAR sensor and 91% of the total
58 cost using the LivoX Mid-40 ([Applanix Alternative 2021](#)). This study examines the feasibility of
59 building a lower cost solution based on the OpenMMS project and the Livox Mid-40 LiDAR sen-
60 sor, but replacing the expensive Applanix INS sensor with a custom solution using off-the-shelf
61 GPS/GNSS (Global Positioning System/Global Navigation Satellite System) modules and inte-
62 grating a less expensive inertial measurement unit (IMU) to form an inertial navigation system
63 (INS).

64 **Hardware**

65 The Livox Mid-40 LiDAR sensor was chosen for its cost and features including, a 260m de-
66 tection range, a 38.4°circular field of view, a 100,000 points per second scan rate, a 2cm range
67 precision, and 0.5°angular precision (Figure 2) ([Mid LiDAR specs- Livox 2021](#)). The non-repetitive
68 scanning pattern of the Livox Mid-40 (Figure 3) means that the longer the integration time the
69 greater the field of view coverage. At 0.1s the the Mid-40 is equivalent to a traditional 32-line
70 LiDAR sensor, while at 0.5s the coverage is equivalent to a 64-line LiDAR sensor ([Mid-40 lidar
71 sensor - Livox 2021](#)). Furthermore, Brazeal et al. utilized a Rigorous Observation Model to test
72 the accuracy of the Risley prism system of the Livox Mid-40 sensor and concluded it is more
73 accurate than the manufacturers specifications (Brazeal et al., [2021b](#)).

74 A canvas of commercially available GNSS modules and IMUs was made to determine if
75 any offered sufficient accuracy at low cost to make the project cost effective. The Ublox ZED-
76 F9P GNSS receiver was selected for its high precision, multi-band GNSS, high update rate, and
77 centimeter-level accuracy ("[ZED-F9P-02B Data sheet](#)" n.d., p. 1). The ZED-F9P is available either
78 as breakout boards from companies such as Sparkfun Electronics and ArduSimple (for develop-
79 ment and incorporation in new designs) or as integrated products from various manufacturers
80 (SparkFun Electronics, n.d.; ArduSimple, n.d.). While ArduSimple offers an RTK Heading Kit with
81 one ZED-F9P on a main board and a second on a daughter board, updating the firmware and
82 configuration on the daughter board often led to timeouts and failures. The ArduSimple mod-
83 ules also took longer to achieve a fix than the Sparkfun breakout boards. For these reasons, two
84 Sparkfun breakout boards were selected, one to serve as a moving base and receive satellite
85 correction data, and the other to serve as the rover (Figure 4). This configuration was selected
86 because Brazeal et al. determined that dual antennae setups are more accurate than a single
87 antenna for UAV based LiDAR mapping systems (Brazeal et al., [2021a](#)). Another advantage of

88 either the ArduSimple RTK Heading Kit or the Sparkfun breakout boards is that they provide
89 access to all the interfaces available on the ZED-F9P chip, although some are mutually exclu-
90 sive, whereas many of the integrated solutions provide limited access to the interfaces and data
91 (SparkFun Electronics, n.d.; ArduSimple, n.d.). Two GNSS multi-band helical antennae were also
92 purchased from Sparkfun for the GNSS modules.

93 For the IMU the Aceinna OpenIMU300ZI EVK development board was selected because it
94 is a 9 DOF (9 degree of freedom) inertial platform which compared favorably with the Applanix
95 APX-18 specifications, offered an open source 16-state Extended State Kalman Filter for fusing
96 the GNSS and IMU data, and offered an open source INS application which supported the ZED-
97 F9P (*Inertial Systems 2021*). Aceinna also provides a development chain which is supported on
98 Windows, Mac, and Linux (*Inertial Systems 2021*).

99 The last pieces of hardware are a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B single board computer, the RPi
100 printed circuit board and LED board, both of which were manufactured by <https://jlcpcb.com/>
101 from the Autodesk Eagle design files downloadable from the OpenMMS website, and a pair of
102 915MHz SiK Radios to send RTCM correction data from the ground base station to the mov-
103 ing base GNSS receiver on the UAV (*OpenMMS Hardware – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3*
104 *documentation 2021*).

105 Software

106 The software for the system uses the OpenMMS Operating System for Livox installed on the
107 Raspberry Pi and the OpenMMS processing software for initial processing (*OpenMMS Software*
108 *– The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation 2021*). The OpenMMS Operating System is
109 licensed under the open source GPL 3 license and is available for download from the OpenMMS
110 data processing tutorial 2 page at [https://www.openmms.org/wp-content/uploads/html/openmms_](https://www.openmms.org/wp-content/uploads/html/openmms_software.html#data-processing-tutorial-2)
111 [software.html#data-processing-tutorial-2](https://www.openmms.org/wp-content/uploads/html/openmms_software.html#data-processing-tutorial-2) (*OpenMMS Software – The OpenMMS Project*
112 *Version 1.3 documentation 2024*). Installation of the OpenMMS Operating System for Livox will
113 also install a version of the OpenMMS firmware used to interface with the Mid-40 LiDAR cam-
114 era and the RGB camera if installed. This study uses a modified version of the firmware that only
115 includes the LiDAR functionality and modified script files.

116 The software for the GNSS modules is the firmware provided by Ublox, and the moving
117 base and rover configuration files available from ArduSimple with slight modifications to turn off
118 export of Ublox binary format messages over USB as these are not necessary and are exported
119 over the UART 1 interface directly to the OpenIMU300ZI development board for processing and
120 fusion with the IMU data (*Configuration Files 2021*; *OpenIMU Developer Manual 2021*; *GPS/INS*
121 *App 2021*).

122 The OpenIMU development board was configured according to the OpenIMU Developer
123 Manual, the GPS/INS application installed, and the GNSS modules connected according to the
124 GPS/INS App documentation (*OpenIMU Developer Manual 2021*; *GPS/INS App 2021*). Aceinna
125 provides a website for development and testing using the Microsoft Visual Code IDE and Plat-
126 form IO and provides a python driver to allow connecting the OpenIMU board to the web in-
127 terface (*OpenIMU Developer Manual 2021*). Development can be done without an internet con-
128 nection, however, visualizing the results through the web interface does require internet access.
129 Additionally, a serial driver is not provided so the python driver must be used with appropri-
130 ate command line options to redirect the output to a comma delimited file (*OpenIMU Developer*
131 *Manual 2021*).

132 **Prototype Construction**

133 Construction of the sensor components was relatively straightforward. The two GNSS mod-
 134 ules and the OpenIMU development board are connected as shown in (Table 1), (Table 2), and
 135 in (Figure 5). This essentially completed the construction of the INS portion of the system.

Table 1 – GNSS Interface Configuration

Interface	GNSS Moving Base	GNSS Rover
UART2	RTCM IN	RTCM IN
UART1	RTCM OUT	UBLOX OUT (to IMU)
USB	No Messages	NMEA OUT (to RPi)

Table 2 – GNSS, OpenIMU, and Radio Pinouts

GNSS Moving Base	GNSS Rover	OpenIMU	Radio on UAV
UART2 RX2			TX
UART2 TX2			RX
UART2 GND			GND
UART1 5v			5v/VCC
UART1 3v3	UART2 3v3		
UART1 TX/MISO	UART2 RX2		
UART1 RX/MOSI	UART2 TX2		
UART1 GND	UART2 GND		
	UART1 TX/MISO	P2 RX	
	UART1 RX/MOSI	P2 TX	
	UART1 GND	P2 GND	
	Control Pin PPS	P4 1PPS	
	USB to RPi	USB to RPi	

136 The firmware on the Livox Mid-40 initially only supports a single return so it is necessary to
 137 update the firmware to the multi-return version available on the Livox Github page (livox, 2021).
 138 This is done using the Livox Viewer software available from the downloads page for the Mid
 139 series LiDAR sensors (*Mid Downloads - Livox 2021*). The next stage was to assemble the elec-
 140 tronics components on the OpenMMS RPi board and the LED board based on the information
 141 provided on the OpenMMS hardware page with the exception of the Adafruit Pro Trinket (3V)
 142 used with a Sony A6000 camera which is not implemented in this prototype (*OpenMMS Hard-
 143 ware – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation 2021*). Connecting the Livox Mid-40 to
 144 the OpenMMS RPi board requires cutting the cable and replacing the Livox converter with a
 145 TTL to RS485 module (*OpenMMS Hardware – The OpenMMS Project Version 1.3 documentation
 146 2021*). The completed prototype is shown below (Figure 6).

147 **Base Station**

148 Because OpenMMS is a post processed kinematics solution (PPK) it needs correction data to
 149 provide accurate position information. To facilitate this a fixed based station was created which
 150 sends correction data to the moving base on the UAV over the 915MHz radio link. There are a
 151 number of tutorials online for setting up a base station including two from Sparkfun Electronics,
 152 however, these rely on third party apps or services to provide the correction data (*How to Build
 153 a DIY GNSS Reference Station - learn.sparkfun.com 2021; Setting up a Rover Base RTK System -*

154 [learn.sparkfun.com 2021](https://learn.sparkfun.com/2021)). Since in the field cellular and internet services may be intermittent or
 155 unavailable a localized solution is necessary. The CentipedeRTK project at <https://centipede.fr/>
 156 was selected as it allows setting up a base station with Ublox ZED-F9P support using a ZED-
 157 F9P breakout board and a Raspberry Pi single board computer ([Projects - CentipedeRTK 2021](#)).
 158 Centipede.fr is a network of Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol (NTRIP) servers
 159 throughout France. The software not only allows setting up a fixed base station but provides a
 160 local NTRIP server as well to send RTCM correction data to the UAV while logging to a Ublox
 161 binary file which can be processed into a Receiver Independent Exchange Format (RINEX) file
 162 of the raw satellite data for later post processing. The software is hosted on github, but Julien
 163 Ancelin provides a ready made Raspian image for Raspberry Pi from his own repository (Julien,
 164 [2021](#)).

165 The base station consists of one Sparkfun ZED-F9P GPS module, an ArduSimple AS-ANT2B-
 166 SUR-L1/L2-25SMA-00 GNSS multi-band survey antenna, a 915MHz telemetry radio (USB), a
 167 Raspberry Pi 3 single board computer, an Official Raspberry Pi 3 case, and a camera tripod. The
 168 Raspian image was written to an SD card and used to boot the Raspberry Pi. Setup is straight-
 169 forward and the ZED-F9P is configured automatically by the software.

170 Total cost to construct the LiDAR sensor and base station are outlined below, significantly
 171 below the cost of the DJI Zenmuse L1 and the cost of an OpenMMS sensor using the Applanix
 172 INS.

Table 3 – 2021/2022 Cost of Major Components (Cost is total cost not per item cost)

Quantity	Item	Cost
1	Livox Mid-40 LiDAR Camera	\$599
3	SparkFun ZED-F9P GPS Modules	\$675
1	OpenIMU300ZI Development Board	\$495
2	Raspberry Pi Single Board Computers	\$240
2	SparkFun GNSS Helix Antenna	\$170
1	ArduSimple Multi-band GNSS Antenna	\$135
	Total	\$2314

173

Results

174 The system was tested at the first century A.D. Roman site of Antiochia ad Cragum in south-
 175 central Turkey in August, 2022. The LiDAR sensor was flown on a DJI Matrice 600 UAV by
 176 professional drone pilots. For logistical reasons the sensor had to be affixed to the drone in the
 177 field using antivibration foam and a one meter rod to mount the GNSS antennae. Initial testing
 178 revealed an issue with the orientation of the Z-axis of the IMU that was corrected later in the pre-
 179 processing stage by subtracting 90° from the pitch angle recorded by the IMU. The preliminary
 180 tests suggested that an altitude of 40m AGL (above ground level) and a forward velocity of 5
 181 m/s would give the best results.

182 An area approximately 7 hectares in area located roughly north-east of what is known as the
 183 Small Bath Area was surveyed in four parts due to battery life of the drone. Issues with the DJI
 184 flight software prevented using an autonomous mission for the survey, so the pattern was flown
 185 manually. The first two portions of the survey were oriented roughly east-west and the remaining
 186 two portions were flown with a north-south orientation to overlap the same area (Figure 7).

187 While the relative positions of the orientations and overlay are encouraging, closer examination
188 reveals gaps between the flight lines as a result of flying the mission manually in windy conditions
189 (Figure 8). A 1m hillshade of the first east-west flight revealed a great deal of noise in the data
190 including the flight lines and remnants of the non-repetitive scanning pattern of the Mid-40
191 LiDAR camera (Figure 9). The noise and non-repetitive scanning pattern are exacerbated in a
192 hillshade of only the ground points from the same first east-west flight (Figure 10). The hillshade
193 was created at 1m resolution to smooth out gaps between the flight lines.

194 Loading the same dataset into CloudCompare and modulating on intensity with the high con-
195 trast color scheme does a better job of representing the scene as trees, shrubs, and even a power
196 line are visible (Figure 11). Rotating the point cloud to provide a profile view presents a better
197 view of the trees, the power line in the background, and topography of the area (Figure 12).

198 The LiDAR and trajectory data, along with the modified OpenMMS firmware and scripts
199 used in collecting the data are available at <https://10.5281/zenodo.13864125>; Rector, 2024.
200 It should be noted only the scripts numbered, 0, 1, 3, and 4 were used.

201

Discussion

202 Further analysis revealed that due to the high outside temperature the battery on the base
203 station failed, so correction data was not being sent to the drone. The lack of ground control
204 points (GCP) prevented a quantitative assessment of the accuracy of the LiDAR point clouds
205 generated. It was not possible to adjust the lever arm measurement from the rover antenna to
206 the IMU once the sensor was mounted and bore sight alignment was not carried out. These may
207 have affected the vertical alignment of the flight lines that are visible in the hillshade images. The
208 inability to fly the mission autonomously contributed to the inconsistent flight path and lack of
209 overlap between flight lines. The non-repetitive scanning pattern of the Mid-40 coupled with
210 the low altitude and velocity created a very dense point cloud on the magnitude of thousands
211 of points per square meter making decimation procedures inconsistent. The low altitude also
212 probably contributed to a very low number of secondary and tertiary returns affecting attempts
213 to classify the point cloud and filter out ground points.

214 The initial results are encouraging and the study generated a number of take-aways to im-
215 prove the system. These include flying autonomous missions at higher altitudes and faster ve-
216 locities to obtain a better dispersion of points. Developing a more robust base station and using
217 georeferenced GPCs. Changing from the two antennae mobile base and rover configuration to a
218 single antenna RTK system. Investigating the use of strip alignment software to correct issues of
219 overlap in flight lines. Upgrading the Mid-40 LiDAR camera to the Livox Avia which offers better
220 range, and both the non-repetitive scan pattern of the Mid-40 and a repetitive scan pattern. Mod-
221 ifying the system to make changes and modifications easier and developing a more user friendly
222 graphical user interface to augment the existing command line interface. Adding an RGB camera
223 to collect aerial photos would help in classifying ground points as discussed by Grammer et al.
224 (Grammer et al., 2017, p. 330). Finally, conducting a series of systematic tests in a variety of
225 contexts to develop a set of protocols for operation.

226

Conclusion

227 This study demonstrated that it is feasible to construct a LiDAR sensor using the Livox Mid-40
228 LiDAR camera and off-the-shelf GNSS modules and IMU hardware at a significantly lower cost.

229 The system is able to collect LiDAR point cloud data that is able to discriminate trees, brush, and
230 even power lines, but also shows a number of areas for improvement. Given the low cost and
231 encouraging results further development is justified.

Figure 1 – Airborne LiDAR scanning (image credit: United States Geological Survey, public domain)

Figure 2 – Livox Mid-40 LiDAR sensor (image credit: Livox)

Figure 3 – Livox Mid-40 LiDAR sensor Non-repetitive Scan Pattern (image credit: Livox)

Figure 4 – Sparkfun GPS-RTK-SMA Breakout (image credit: Sparkfun Electronics)

Figure 5 – Component connections (GNSS Moving Base lower left, OpenIMU upper right) (image credit: author)

Figure 6 – Assembled prototype Mid-40 LiDAR sensor (top view and side view) (image credit: author)

Figure 7 – Small bath area four flights showing overlap (red-green-blue are east-west, red-blue are north-south) (image credit: author)

Figure 8 – Small bath area two flights north-south showing gaps in flight lines (image credit: author)

Figure 9 – Small bath area east-west first flight 1 meter hillshade (image credit: author)

Figure 10 – Small bath area east-west first flight 1 meter hillshade ground points (image credit: author)

Figure 11 – Small bath area east-west first flight (image credit: author)

Figure 12 – Small bath area east-west first flight profile view (image credit: author)

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250

Conflict of interest disclosure

251 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of
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253

Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

254 Data are available online (<https://10.5281/zenodo.13864125>; Rector, 2024
255 Script and codes are available online (<https://10.5281/zenodo.13864125>; Rector, 2024

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